

This is the generalised absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is simple, it is therefore complex, however, if it is complex, it is therefore simple. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is complex. However, if it is complex, it is therefore simple, however, if it is simple, it is therefore complex. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is simple. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either complex or simple.

This set is timed as 22:01, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.